

D 3.2 Approach to identify local requirements for selecting DRR approaches

Disclaimer: The content of this document represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission does not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project is funded by the European Union Civil Protection, under grant agreement No 783232

Table of contents

Table of Contents

History	3
List of abbreviations.....	4
Executive summary	5
Introduction.....	6
Steps Towards Identifying the Local Requirements	7
The Overall Approach.....	8
Relevant Sendai DRR Framework of Action Provisions.....	9
Sendai Global Targets and DRR in Solotvyno, Ukraine.....	12
Guiding Risk Governance Framework.....	15
Guiding Risk Evaluation Approach.....	17
Policy - Practice Gaps	18
Science - Policy Gaps	19
Ukraine Risk Governance Transition Requirements.....	20
ImProDiReT and other Projects' Solution Requirements	21

History

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
0.1	16-11-18	Initial Outline	Lucia, Abby, Kenny
0.2	20-11-18	Revised ToC, Literature Review and Backbone Chapters	Abby Onencan
0.3	30-11-18	Added methodology section with all the relevant Figures (Figure 1-3), and the relevant Sendai provisions in Box 1-4, consolidation and formatting	Abby Onencan
0.4	10-12-18	Added the text on the guiding risk governance and risk evaluation approach	Abby Onencan
0.5	17-12-18	Added the Figures on Policy-Practice gaps (Figure 4) and the Science Policy gaps (Figure 5)	Abby Onencan
0.6	21-12-18	Added the Figures on the Transition and Solution requirements (Figure 6 and 7)	Abby Onencan
0.7	23-12-18	Added the section on future follow-up work. More consolidation of input and document formatting	Abby Onencan

List of abbreviations

ImProDiReT Improving Disaster Risk Reduction in Transcarpathia

WP Work Package

DoA Description of Action

DRR Disaster Risk Reduction

TUD Technische Universiteit Delft

IGS NASU Institute of Geological Sciences National Academy of Sciences Of Ukraine

MSFS The Main School of Fire Service

ARDZ Institution Regional Development Agency of Zakarpattia Oblast

RAN Resilience Advisors Network

UCPM Union Civil Protection Mechanism

EU European Union

Executive summary

ImProDiReT project was launched in March 2018 with a lifetime of 24 months and it aims to empower communities within the Transcarpathian region in Ukraine with innovative socio-technical solutions to help them reconnect, respond to, and recover from crisis situations.

The main objectives of the project is to foster social innovation during crises for safeguarding communities during critical scenarios from inaccurate, distrusted, and overhyped information, and for raising citizen and community awareness of crisis situations by providing them with filtered, validated, enriched, high quality, and actionable knowledge. Community decision-making will be assisted by automated methods for real-time, intelligent processing and linking of crowdsourced crisis information.

Introduction

ImProDiReT project was launched in March 2018 with a lifetime of 24 months and it aims to empower communities within the Transcarpathian region in Ukraine with innovative socio-technical solutions to help them reconnect, respond to, and recover from crisis situations.

The Transcarpathian region is situated in the West of Ukraine. Geographically the region is dominated by the northern part of the Carpathian mountain range, which stretches from Poland and Slovakia in a horse shoe form into Romania, crossing Ukraine. The population of Transcarpathia is multi-ethnic, with several large minority groups, for example Romanians, Hungarians, Russians, and Romas.

Since the collapse of the Union of the Soviet Socialistic Republics (USSR) the logical connections between Ukrainian institutes and institutions with relevant data on hazards and risk of disasters and the local and regional administration were disturbed. An open, transparent exchange of information has become increasingly difficult at all levels, also in addressing cross-cutting issues. The UCPM Scoping mission to the Sotvyno noted this as a major obstacle to come to a good, all-inclusive assessment. In respect to the Sendai, framework problems can be seen in the field of understanding risks, risk reduction governance and investing in risk reduction management.

The main objectives of the project are to foster social innovation during crises for safeguarding communities during critical scenarios from inaccurate, distrusted, and overhyped information, and for raising citizen and community awareness of crisis situations by providing them with filtered, validated, enriched, high quality, and actionable knowledge. Community decision-making will be assisted by automated methods for real-time, intelligent processing and linking of crowdsourced crisis information.

Methodology for Identifying the Local Context

Steps Towards Identifying the Local Requirements

- We developed the methodology based on some policy documents, reports, interview transcripts, relevant publications, and field visits and meetings with the local stakeholders.
- This deliverable demonstrates how local requirements can be identified and linked with existing literature, identifying common and relevant information, as well as any gaps between guidelines, frameworks and the local application.
- The deliverable also documents the process that TU Delft used to develop the approach so that it can be replicated in other contexts.
- The interviews conducted in June and July 2018 in Kiev, Uzhhorod, and Solotvyno guided the overall development of the D3.2 methodology to identify local requirements for selecting DRR approaches. Before August 2018, TU Delft had already started conceptualizing and agreeing internally what should be the content of D3.2.
- Also, to guide the risk evaluation approach processes, WP 3 designed a participatory GIS and CS methodology aimed at engaging the citizens in the entire Earth Observation (EO) project cycle [1]. The scientific article has been [published open access by the remote-sensing journal](#). The methodology also seeks to address previous CS project challenges related to data quality, data interoperability, citizen-motivation, and participation.
- The high-level requirements are drawn from the SENDAI framework of action [2, 3] and the three pillars of active citizen engagement, as enshrined in Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration [4] and the Aarhus Convention [5-8].
- The primary input of the D 3.1 methodology is the Haklay (2018) approach for participatory mapping and CS [9], and the Reed (2009) stakeholder analysis framework [10]. The proposed methodology comprises of three main parts: system analysis, stakeholder analysis, and a six-step methodology. WP3 designed the six-step methodology using an iterative and flexible approach, to take account of unforeseen changes. Future research will focus on implementing the methodology and evaluating its effectiveness in the Solotvyno Saltmine case study in Ukraine.
- After that, TU Delft began the process of identifying the relevant elements from various frameworks, practices and guidelines, and the determination of their applicability to the local context.

The Methodology

The Overall Approach

- The approach was initiated by conducting key informant interviews in Kiev, Uzzhorod and Solotvyno in June and July 2018.
- Based on the findings of the interview, we conducted a detailed review of the Sendai Framework for disaster risk reduction to identify the policy – practice gaps.
- However, in the process of the field visits and the literature review, we also identified related science – policy gaps mainly occasioned by the absence of data, deep uncertainty and stakeholder complexities that had an impact on the Solotvyno community’s perceptions of risk.
- Therefore, the approach is two-pronged, with a focus on identifying the following gaps and the subsequent requirements (see Figure 3):
 1. The Science-Policy mismatches; and
 2. The Policy – Practice mismatches.

Figure 1. Approach for Application of Sendai Framework in Solotvyno, Ukraine

- D3.2 will implement the first part of the approach, where the gaps are identified and the subsequent requirements.
- WP4 will implement the latter part of the approach (testing the requirements and developing a community-based action plan) in collaboration with WP3.

Relevant Sendai DRR Framework of Action Provisions

- The Sendai Framework acknowledges that there will always be a gap between the science – policy, and practice while attempting to apply the provisions at the local level. This challenge is articulated in some Sendai provisions as highlighted in Box 1.

BOX 1: PROVISIONS DEALING WITH SENDAI SCIENCE – POLICY -PRACTICE GAPS

Article 19. Drawing from the principles contained in the Yokohama Strategy for a Safer World: Guidelines for Natural Disaster Prevention, Preparedness and Mitigation and its Plan of Action¹⁰ and the Hyogo Framework for Action, the implementation of the present Framework will be guided by the following principles, **while taking into account national circumstances, and consistent with domestic laws as well as international obligations and commitments:**

(f) While the enabling, guiding and coordinating role of national and federal State Governments remain essential, **it is necessary to empower local authorities and local communities to reduce disaster risk, including through resources, incentives, and decision-making responsibilities, as appropriate;**

(i) While the drivers of disaster risk may be local, national, regional or global in scope, **disaster risks have local and specific characteristics that must be understood for the determination of measures to reduce disaster risk;**

(m) Developing countries, in particular, the least developed countries, small island developing

States, landlocked developing countries and African countries, as well as middle-income and other countries facing specific disaster risk challenges, **need adequate, sustainable and timely provision of support, including through finance, technology transfer and capacity building from developed countries and partners tailored to their needs and priorities, as identified by them.**

Article 21. In their approach to disaster risk reduction, States, regional and international organizations and other relevant stakeholders should take into consideration the key activities listed under each of these four priorities and should implement them, as appropriate, taking into consideration respective capacities and capabilities, in line with national laws and regulations.

Article 22. In the context of increasing global interdependence, concerted international cooperation, an enabling international environment, and **means of implementation are needed to stimulate and contribute to developing the knowledge, capacities, and motivation for disaster risk reduction at all levels, in particular for developing countries.**

- Therefore D3.2 is in furtherance of the Sendai provisions that seek to bridge the gap between what science has provided, what the policy has stipulated and the reality on the ground.
- The main framework of analysis is the Sendai Framework [3] and the Technical guidance for monitoring and reporting on progress in achieving the global targets of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (New edition) [2].
- The methodology is designed with a core focus on:
 1. The seven Sendai global targets; and
 2. The four Sendai priorities of Action;
 3. Specific Sendai provisions that relate to the ImProDiReT project.

- The seven Sendai global targets that we also focused on are outlined in Box 2.

BOX 2: THE SENDAI FRAMEWORK OF ACTION SEVEN GLOBAL TARGETS

Article 18. To support the assessment of global progress in achieving the outcome and goal of the present Framework, seven global targets have been agreed. These targets will be measured at the global level and will be complemented by work to develop appropriate indicators. National targets and indicators will contribute to the achievement of the outcome and goal of the present Framework. The seven global targets are:

- a) Substantially reduce global disaster mortality by 2030, aiming to lower the average per 100,000 global mortality rate in the decade 2020–2030 compared to the period 2005–2015;
- b) Substantially reduce the number of affected people globally by 2030, aiming to lower the average global figure per 100,000 in the decade 2020–2030 compared to the period 2005–2015;
- c) Reduce direct disaster economic loss about global gross domestic product (GDP) by 2030;
- d) Substantially reduce disaster damage to critical infrastructure and disruption of basic services, among them health and educational facilities, including through developing their resilience by 2030;
- d) Substantially increase the number of countries with national and local disaster risk reduction strategies by 2020;
- e) Substantially enhance international cooperation to developing countries through adequate and sustainable support to complement their national actions for implementation of the present Framework by 2030;
- f) Substantially increase the availability of and access to multi-hazard early warning systems and disaster risk information and assessments to people by 2030.

- The four Sendai priorities of Action are outlined in Box 3.

BOX 3: SENDAI PRIORITIES FOR ACTION

Article 20. Taking into account the experience gained through the implementation of the Hyogo Framework for Action, and in pursuance of the expected outcome and goal, there is a need for focused action within and across sectors by States at local, national, regional and global levels in the following four priority areas:

Priority 1: Understanding disaster risk.

Priority 2: Strengthening disaster risk governance to manage disaster risk.

Priority 3: Investing in disaster risk reduction for resilience.

Priority 4: Enhancing disaster preparedness for effective response and to “Build Back Better” in recovery, rehabilitation, and reconstruction.

- The specific risk disaster risk governance provisions that guide the development of the methodology are outlined in Box 4.

BOX 4: STRENGTHENING DISASTER RISK GOVERNANCE TO MANAGE DISASTER RISK

Article 26. Disaster risk governance at the national, regional and global levels is of great importance for an effective and efficient management of disaster risk. Clear vision, plans, competence, guidance and coordination within and across sectors, as well as participation of relevant stakeholders, are needed. Strengthening disaster risk governance for prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response, recovery and rehabilitation is therefore necessary and fosters collaboration and partnership across mechanisms and institutions for the implementation of instruments relevant to disaster risk reduction and sustainable development. National and local levels

Article 27. To achieve this, it is important:

- To mainstream and integrate disaster risk reduction within and across all sectors and review and promote the coherence and further development, as appropriate, of national and local frameworks of laws, regulations and public policies, which, by defining roles and responsibilities, guide the public and private sectors in: (i) addressing disaster risk in publicly owned, managed or regulated services and infrastructures; (ii) promoting and providing incentives, as relevant, for actions by persons, households, communities and businesses; (iii) enhancing relevant mechanisms and initiatives for disaster risk transparency, which may include financial incentives, public awareness-raising and training initiatives, reporting requirements and legal and administrative measures; and (iv) putting in place coordination and organizational structures;
- To carry out an assessment of the technical, financial and administrative disaster risk management capacity to deal with the identified risks at the local and national levels;
- To encourage the establishment of necessary mechanisms and incentives to ensure high levels of compliance with the existing safety-enhancing provisions of sectoral laws and regulations, including those addressing land use and urban planning, building codes, environmental and resource management and health and safety standards, and update them, where needed, to ensure an adequate focus on disaster risk management;
- To develop and strengthen, as appropriate, mechanisms to follow up, periodically assess and publicly report on progress on national and local plans; and promote public scrutiny and encourage institutional debates, including by parliamentarians and other relevant officials, on progress reports of local and national plans for disaster risk reduction;
- To assign, as appropriate, clear roles and tasks to community representatives within disaster risk management institutions and processes and decision-making through relevant legal frameworks, and undertake comprehensive public and community consultations during the development of such laws and regulations to support their implementation;
- To establish and strengthen government coordination forums composed of relevant stakeholders at the national and local levels, such as national and local platforms for disaster risk reduction, and a designated national focal point for implementing the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030.
- To empower local authorities, as appropriate, through regulatory and financial means to work and coordinate with civil society, communities and indigenous peoples and migrants in disaster risk management at the local level;
- To encourage parliamentarians to support the implementation of disaster risk reduction by developing new or amending relevant legislation and setting budget allocations;
- To formulate public policies, where applicable, aimed at addressing the issues of prevention or relocation, where possible, of human settlements in disaster risk-prone zones, subject to national law and legal systems.

DRR and Solotvyno, Ukraine

Sendai Global Targets and DRR in Solotvyno, Ukraine

- The Sendai Framework provisions are high-level provisions with concrete actions that should be implemented at the national and local level.
- However, the high-level provisions are unable to take into account the particular circumstance of each DRR case study.
- To illustrate the enormous gap between the policy provisions and practice, we picked six of the seven global targets and matched them with the Solotvyno case study.
- Based on the content in Figure 2, it is evident that in the case of Solotvyno, Ukraine, there is a huge gap that remains to be filled because none of the targets has been achieved.

Figure 2. Sendai Framework and DRR in Solotvyno, Ukraine

D3.2 Approach to identify local requirements for selecting DRR approaches

- The policy-practice gap is evidenced by:
 - The indirect mortality rates are not certain;
 - The affected persons cannot be ascertained with the current data, and there is minimal effort to reduce the number of affected persons;
 - The economic loss is not well documented and what is not known cannot be adequately addressed;
 - The infrastructural damage is still ongoing, as the mining company objects are still on site and the land continues to subside, with minimal effort to remedy the situation, at the local level;
 - There is no DRR strategy at the municipality and minimal efforts to initiate an early warning system.
 - European attempts to consolidate DRR data seem to be slow, and the quality of data from Ukraine is of lower quality compared to most of the European countries.
 - Eventually, if this European Union initiative is successful, the data being collected might only contain sudden disasters and leave out the slow-onset disasters, like the one facing the Sotvyno residents.

- The science – policy gap is evidenced by:
 - Deep uncertainties that science cannot provide answers to which is contrary to the spirit of Sendai that is data and evidence-driven.
 - Deep complexities are facing a small and extremely complex community. These complexities are due to many reasons that will be highlighted later in the document. However, one of the core reasons for these complex social system is the Sotvyno stakeholder complexity.
 - Stakeholder complexity is due to the location of the Sotvyno, it is a border town, with a small wooden bridge separating Romania from Ukraine.
 - Stakeholder complexity is evidenced by:
 - (a) Mixed, multiple nationalities with regular movements from one international boundary to another. Any DRR action that is not coordinated with the neighboring countries may fail because the residents of Sotvyno are constantly moving borders.
 - (b) Loss of livelihood after the closure of the mines led to increased vulnerability and increased movements across the border. Most miners started conducting border trade, which increased the borderland complexity.
 - (c) The mixed languages (Mainly Hungarian, Ukrainian, Romanian and Czech Republic), mixed religions and strong religious beliefs, segregation within the small municipality (separate housing blocks, schools, churches, and religious institutions for the different nationalities), is counter any effort to integrate the community.
 - (d) A rich cultural background from the heterogeneous community.

- The biggest challenge for a scientist would be to accept that in a complex socio-technical system like Sotvyno where there is very high uncertainty occasioned by poor governance systems and weak DRR information management systems, there may never be a blueprint. Therefore, this deliverable is the first step in seeking to address some of the challenges faced when seeking to apply the Sendai Framework at the local level. D 3.2 is in response to some of the following questions:
 - (a) Without a blueprint, how can scientists determine the extent of risk, how will they calculate the probability that a particular risk will happen in the future?
 - (b) Can they rely on community-based evaluations of risk without having tangible evidence to support the decision-making?

D3.2 Approach to identify local requirements for selecting DRR approaches

- (c) Even if they have evidence, what is the community is cognitively biased and possess risk perceptions that are contrary to the Sendai framework provisions?
 - (d) What if the community accepts a high risk, due to economic reasons, livelihoods, religion, culture, poverty, family ties or place attachment.
 - (e) What can a scientist do if his models fail to model vulnerability and the social complexity within Solotvyno?
- To be able to answer some of these questions, we not only relied on the Sendai Framework provisions. The governance provisions in priority 2 of the Sendai Framework were mirrored against the OECD Indicator Framework and Evolving Practices. The scientific provisions were mirrored against the Klinke and Renn (2002) risk evaluation and management approach that assesses risk-based, precaution-based and discourse-based strategies.

Governance Framework and Risk Evaluation Approach

Guiding Risk Governance Framework

- The OECD Governance Indicator Framework [11] was developed within the OECD Water Governance Initiative through a bottom-up and multi-stakeholder approach over 2015-2017 and pilot-tested by 11 institutions at different scales and in different geographic and socio-economic contexts.
- It provides a voluntary multi-stakeholder self-assessment tool to understand the performance of governance systems at city, basin, regional or national scales. Its primary objective is to stimulate a transparent, neutral, open, inclusive and forward-looking dialogue across stakeholders on what works, what does not, what should be improved and who can do what.
- Under D3.2, the framework was modified to the case of Solotvyno as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 3. Solotvyno, Ukraine Risk Governance Framework, Modified for the OECD Governance Indicator Framework [11], (p. 5)

- The indicator framework is composed of a traffic light system based on 36 input and process indicators and a checklist of broader governance conditions. It concludes with an action plan to prepare and prioritize actions over the short, medium and long run.
- The Principles are clustered around three main dimensions:

D3.2 Approach to identify local requirements for selecting DRR approaches

1. The effectiveness of governance relates to the contribution of governance to defining clear sustainable water policy goals and targets at different levels of government, to implement those policy goals, and to meet expected objectives or targets.
 2. The efficiency of governance relates to the contribution of governance to maximizing the benefits of sustainable water management and welfare at the least cost to society.
 3. Trust and engagement in governance relate to the contribution of governance to building public confidence and ensuring the inclusiveness of stakeholders through democratic legitimacy and fairness for society at large.
- The OECD Governance Indicator Framework is the first step towards developing a checklist and a DRR action plan.

Guiding Risk Evaluation Approach

- To remain focused on the task we limited the science-policy analysis to risk evaluation so as to inform D3.3, that will focus on developing and implementing a community-based risk evaluation approach.
- A new approach to risk evaluation and selection of risk management strategies is presented in Klinke and Renn (2002) [12].
- The approach consists of a risk classification scheme that is used to select or recommend risk management strategies, based on the magnitude or value of the included characteristics.
- This classification scheme was established as a part of a project conducted on behalf of the German Government's Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU).
- We refer to this classification scheme as the WBGU scheme in the remaining part of this paper. The WBGU scheme includes seven characteristics, in addition to the two traditional characteristics included in technical risk analysis: the extent of damage and the probability of occurrence.
- The seven additional characteristics are used to describe aspects of uncertainty and the extent of damages, e.g., delay effects and the geographical dispersion of the damages, the discrepancy between those who bear the risk and those who enjoy the benefits of the risk, and for the potential of mobilization, the risk may have.
- The WBGU scheme presented in Klinke and Renn (2002) [12] includes nine characteristics. These are:
 - Extent of damage
 - Probability of occurrence
 - Incertitude
 - Ubiquity
 - Persistency
 - Reversibility
 - Delay effects
 - Violation of equity and
 - Potential of mobilization.
- Incertitude is defined as an overall indicator of different uncertainty components.
- Ubiquity, persistency, reversibility and delay effect are all used to give a further description or characterization of the extent of the damage.
- Potential of mobilization is to be understood as a violation of individual, social and cultural interests and values generating social conflicts and psychological reactions by individuals and groups who feel inflicted by the risk consequences. The potential of mobilization could also result from perceived inequities in the distribution of risk and benefits.
- The two characteristics: the violation of equity and the potential of mobilization are different from the other characteristics, as they represent another dimension of risk—a judgment of how people feel, value and judge risk. We refer to such judgments as 'risk valuation' in the following.

Gap Analysis

Policy – Practice Gaps

Figure 4. Policy-Practice Gaps

Science - Policy Gaps

- UNKNOWN EXTENT OF DAMAGE**
 - # of Disaster Mortality;
 - # of Affected persons
 - Direct Economic Losses; and
 - Damage to Critical infrastructure and destruction of basic services.

- PROBABILITY OF OCCURENCE**
 - Uncertainty on what is happening below the ground after the mines were flooded;
 - Poor risk data management systems;
 - Short-term risk assessments by various scientists with limited coordination or consolidation of data.

- INCERTITUDE**
 - Hard to deal with random events;
 - Religion, culture & Ignorance and its effects on risk perception;
 - Lack of dis-aggregated DRR data

- VIOLATION OF EQUITY**
 - Current financing of projects in Solotvyno is increasing risk and vulnerability; and
 - There is a discrepancy between the businesses that are enjoying the benefits and the community that has to bear the risks.

Broad Category of Gaps

- Governance**
- Scientific**

3 INVEST

Science-Policy Gaps

Identified scientific challenges to implementing the Sendai Priorities for Action in **Solotvyyo, Ukraine**.

Priority 1. Understanding disaster risk;

Priority 2. Strengthening DR governance to manage DR

Priority 3. Investing inDRR for resilience; and

Priority 4. Enhancing disaster preparedness for effective response and to "Build Back Better" in recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction.

4 BUILD BACK BETTER

- MOBILIZATION POTENTIAL**
 - Environmental degradation by the mining company without managing the freshwater systems led to the subsequent subsidence and mine collapse;
 - Closing of the mines led to a loss of jobs, livelihood, damage to houses and overall safety concerns;
 - There is a violation of individual, family, social and cultural interests and values which is generating social tensions by groups of people who perceive that there is inequitable risk distribution.

- DELAY EFFECT**
 - Long time latency between the initial event (flooding of the mines) and the actual impact of damage.
 - Slow-onset disasters are given less priority over sudden disasters.
 - Action by the business community is increasing risk & vulnerability

- UBIQUITY**
 - Contested geographical dispersion of potential damage due to previous risk maps and deformed buildings;
 - The available space and in-situ information is not sufficient to undertake a comprehensive risk evaluation and joint decision-making.

- PERSISTENCY**
 - Since the disaster is slow-onset, there is a temporal extension of potential damage;
 - It is hard to assess the risk based on historical data because there are no reliable baselines and no consistent periodical assessment of the hydro-geological risks.

1. UNDERSTAND

2. STRENGTHEN

Figure 5. Science - Policy Gaps

Transition and Solution Requirements

Ukraine Risk Governance Transition Requirements

- BABOK V2 describes Transition Requirements as “capabilities that the solution must have in order to facilitate a transition from the current state of the enterprise to a desired future state, but that will not be needed once that transition is complete. They are differentiated from other requirements types because they are always temporary and because they cannot be developed until both an existing and new solution are defined.”
- In simpler terms, transition requirements are what needs to be done to transition to the solution. The solution is an improved disaster risk governance system in Solotvyno.

Figure 6. Risk Governance Transition Requirements

ImProDiReT and other Projects' Solution Requirements

- Solution Requirements are functional and qualitative. Therefore they describe behavior and environmental conditions that a business solution (project in our case) must have to remain effective.

Figure 7. ImProDiReT and Other Solotvyno Projects' Solution Requirements

Proposed Future Follow-up Work

- Based on the identified gaps and requirements, there may be a need for further follow-up work at the project and country level to ensure that some if not all, the requirements are satisfied.
- To guide the process, we propose three instruments:
 1. A simple monitoring and evaluation approach with clear and measurable indicators to assess the level of fulfillment of the requirements;
 2. A checklist of questions; and
 3. An action plan.
- The accompanying checklist of questions should focus on the implementation of the Transition and Solution requirements.
- Respondents can answer the questions through yes, no, in development or not applicable. Also, they should be able to provide sources/references in order to cross-check the assessment.
- A part of the Checklist (only relevant to the ImProDiReT project and the risk evaluation process) will form part of D3.3, the risk evaluation approach because a responsive a governance system is improved DRR interventions and a weak governance system aggravates the current state of affairs.
- The Action Plan is the proposed final step in the self-assessment process. It should include actions already in place or planned over the short, medium and long run for each of the requirements and corresponding indicators. The objective is for stakeholders to determine what collective actions can be taken to DR governance system and the scientific concerns that did not reach a satisfactory level of implementation in comparison to the Sendai Framework for Action.

References

1. Onencan, A.M., K. Meesters, and B. Van de Walle, *Methodology for Participatory GIS Risk Mapping and Citizen Science for Solotvyno Salt Mines*. Remote Sensing, 2018. **10**(11): p. 1828.
2. United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR), *Technical guidance for monitoring and reporting on progress in achieving the global targets of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction*, Open-ended Intergovernmental Expert Working Group on Indicators and Terminology Related to Disaster Risk Reduction (A/71/644), Editor. 2017, United Nations General Assembly. p. 180.
3. UNISDR, U.N.O. *Sendai framework for disaster risk reduction 2015–2030*. 2015. UNISDR Sendai, Japan.
4. Declaration, R., *Rio declaration on environment and development*. 1992.
5. Wates, J., *Aarhus Convention: A Driving Force for Environmental Democracy*, The. J. Eur. Env'tl. & Plan. L., 2005. **2**: p. 2.
6. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), *Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters*, E.C.o.E. Policy, Editor. 1998: Aarhus, Denmark.
7. Stec, S. and S. Casey-Lefkowitz, *The Aarhus Convention: an implementation guide*. 2000: The Commission.
8. Kravchenko, S., *The Aarhus Convention and innovations in compliance with multilateral environmental agreements*. Colo. J. Int'l Env'tl. L. & Pol'y, 2007. **18**: p. 1.

D3.2 Approach to identify local requirements for selecting DRR approaches

9. Haklay, M. and L. Francis, eds. *Participatory GIS and community-based citizen science for environmental justice action*. The Routledge Handbook of Environmental Justice, ed. J. Chakraborty, Walker, G. and Holifield, R. 2018, Routledge: Abingdon. 297-308.
10. Reed, M.S., et al., *Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management*. Journal of environmental management, 2009. **90**(5): p. 1933-1949.
11. OECD *The OECD Governance Indicator Framework*. 2015.
12. Klinke, A. and O. Renn, *A New Approach to Risk Evaluation and Management: Risk-Based, Precaution-Based, and Discourse-Based Strategies 1*. Risk Analysis: An International Journal, 2002. **22**(6): p. 1071-1094.